

Chemistry of Aminobenzothiazoles: *N*-2-Benzothiazolylcyanamides, Related Thiocarbamides, Isothiocarbamides and Carbamides

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Several derivatives of thiocarbamides, cyanamides, carbamides, and isothiocarbamides containing a 2-aminobenzothiazole or substituted 2-aminobenzothiazole group, are described.

In continuation of the work reported earlier (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 621) the present communication describes the preparation of certain *N*-2-benzothiazolylthiocarbamides, cyanamides, and related derivatives.

Although the formation of *N*-2-benzothiazolylthiocarbamide (I) as an intermediate in the hydrochloric acid hydrolysis of phenylthiouret to 2-aminobenzothiazole had been envisaged by Fromm (*Annalen*, 1893, 275, 20; Kurzer, *Chem. Rev.*, 1956, 56, 154), this substance does not appear to have been prepared so far. The most obvious probable methods of obtaining it appear to be the following: (i) the pyrolysis of 2-aminobenzothiazole and thiocarbamide analogous to the reaction of aniline and thiocarbamide leading to phenylthiocarbamide and thiocarbaniide; (ii) isomerisation of 2-aminobenzothiazole thiocyanate analogous to the isomeric change of aniline thiocyanate to phenylthiocarbamide; (iii) interaction of 2-chlorobenzothiazole with thiocarbamide similar to the reaction of amines with the former; (iv) oxidative cyclisation (cf. this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 155) of 1-phenyl-2-thio-4-*S*-benzylbiuret to *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide and subsequent reduction of the latter to *N*-2-benzothiazolylthiocarbamide; (v) the preparation of *N*-2-benzothiazolylcyanamide (II) by the action of bromocyanogen with 2-aminobenzothiazole (III) and the thiohydrolysis of the cyanamide so obtained into *N*-2-benzothiazolylthiocarbamide (I).

(Where R is H or Me or Ph and X is Me group or hydrogen either in 3 or 6 position. Bz represents benzyl group).

The reactions (i) and (ii) under a variety of conditions afforded identical products. In the case of 2-aminobenzothiazole, this is a substance, $C_{10}H_{13}N_3S_2$, m.p. 248°, which has not been identified so far. The 3-methyl-2-iminobenzothiazole similarly gave a compound

$C_{20}H_{21}N_3S_4$, m.p. 262°. The reaction (iii) gave, what appears to be *S*-2-benzothiazolyl-isothiouonium chloride (*Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1961, Part III, 101) and the reaction (iv) did not result in the expected *N*-2-benzothiazolyl-*S*-alkylisothiocarbamide, but an isomeric 5-phenylamino-3-*S*-benzyl-1,2,4-thiadiazole was formed instead. The above sequence of changes (III to I), as envisaged in (v), was realised though the yields were not uniformly good.

The *N*-2-benzothiazolylcyanamides (II) on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid, as was expected, afforded the related carbamides. The *N*-2-benzothiazolylthiocarbamides on benzylation with benzyl chloride formed the related *S*-benzylisothiocarbamides (V). Several compounds of the type (I) to (V) have been prepared (*vide infra*).

EXPERIMENTAL

The required 2-aminobenzothiazoles were prepared by the oxidative cyclisation of the appropriate aryl-substituted thiocarbamides in inert solvents like benzene or chloroform (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2023, 2270; 1926, 3085). 2-Chlorobenzothiazole was prepared by the action of thionyl chloride on 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (*cf.* Suresh, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1959, Part III, 134).

Mercaptobenzothiazole (50 g.) and thionyl chloride (75 c.c.) were mixed and kept without any extraneous solvent for a week at room temperature. It was then poured into excess of water and steam distilled, yielding 39.5 g. (79%) of chlorobenzothiazole, the maximum yield so far observed.

Bromocyanogen was prepared by the interaction of bromine and aqueous potassium cyanide (Scholl, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1822; Williams, "Cyanogen Compounds", 1948, 2nd ed., p. 9).

(I). (a) *Pyrolysis of 2-Aminobenzothiazole and Thiocarbamide*

An intimate equimolecular mixture of 2-aminobenzothiazole and thiocarbamide was heated at 160° in an oil bath for about 15 minutes; evolution of ammonia and hydrogen sulphide was noted. The product was poured into cold dilute hydrochloric acid to remove the unchanged 2-aminobenzothiazole and thiocarbamide. The residue was collected and crystallised from solvents like glacial acetic acid and chlorobenzene; m.p. 248°. It is nondesulphurisable with sodium plumbite solution. (Found: C, 53.69; H, 3.03; N, 15.36; S, 27.82. $C_{12}H_{15}N_3S_4$ requires C, 52.98; H, 3.31; N, 15.45; S, 28.25%).

(b) *Pyrolysis of 2-Aminobenzothiazole Thiocyanate*.—On mixing concentrated aqueous solutions of 2-aminobenzothiazole hydrochloride and ammonium thiocyanate, 2-aminobenzothiazole thiocyanate was obtained as a white precipitate, m.p. 168°. It was heated at its m.p. for about one hour and poured into excess of cold water. The solid collected was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 248°. (Found: N, 15.35; S, 27.85. $C_{12}H_{15}N_3S_4$ requires N, 15.45; S, 28.25%). It was found to be identical with the product obtained by the pyrolysis of 2-aminobenzothiazole and thiocarbamide.

(c) *Pyrolysis of 3-Methyl-2-iminobenzothiazole and Thiocarbamide*.—An intimate mixture of 3-methyl-2-iminobenzothiazole and thiocarbamide was heated at 160° for about 20-25 minutes. The mixture was poured into HCl (cold, dilute) to remove the

unchanged reactants. The solid residue was collected and crystallised from absolute ethanol and acetic acid, m.p. 262°. It was not desulphurisable with sodium plumbite solution. (Found: C, 54.76; H, 3.96; N, 14.04; S, 26.1. $C_{23}H_{21}N_3S_4$ requires C, 55.75; H, 4.24; N, 14.14; S, 25.85%).

(d) *Pyrolysis of 3-Methyl-2-iminobenzothiazole Thiocyanate*.—3-Methyl-2-iminobenzothiazole thiocyanate was prepared by mixing aqueous solutions of 3-methyl-2-iminobenzothiazole hydrochloride and ammonium thiocyanate; m.p. 178°. It was heated at 130-40° for about 2 hours. The product was poured into excess of cold water and the solid product was collected and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 262°. (Found: N, 14.09; S, 26%). It is identical with the product obtained in (c).

(II). Interaction of 2-Chlorobenzothiazole with Thiocarbamide

An intimate mixture of 2-chlorobenzothiazole and thiocarbamide was heated at 30-40° for about 1 hour. The pasty mass obtained was washed with dry acetone to remove the unchanged reactants. The residue left was found to be acidic; m.p. 158°. It decomposed in contact with water yielding 2-mercaptobenzothiazole, cyanamide, and carbamide. It gave a picrate, m.p. 172°. (Found: C, 39.6; H, 3.13; N, 16.83; S, 26.74. $C_8H_8N_3ClS_2$ requires C, 39.1; H, 3.25; N, 17.5; S, 26.06%). Equivalent weight of the hydrochloride was found titrimetrically. (Found: Equiv., 243.3. $C_8H_8N_3S_2Cl$ requires equiv., 245.5).

This substance was identified as *S*-2-benzothiazolyliothiuronium chloride. The same product was obtained by refluxing an equimolecular mixture of 2-chlorobenzothiazole and thiocarbamide in dry acetone for about 15 minutes.

(III). Oxidation of 1-Phenyl-2-thio-4-S-benzylbiuret in Benzene with Bromine

1-Phenyl-2-thio-4-S-benzylbiuret was prepared by heating a mixture of *S*-benzylisothiuronium chloride and phenyl isothiocyanate for half-an-hour and by subsequent basification of the product; m.p. 116°. (Found: N, 13.88. $C_{13}H_{13}N_3S_2$ requires N, 13.95%). Hydrochloride, m.p. 165°. (Found: Equiv., 339.8. $C_{13}H_{13}N_3S_2$, HCl requires equiv., 337.5).

A clear solution of this isodithiobiuret was taken in benzene and molecular bromine was added till the colour of bromine persisted. The solid product thus obtained was filtered, dissolved in water, and basified. The base was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 154°. (Found: N, 13.68; S, 21.52. $C_{13}H_{13}N_3S_2$ requires N, 14.04; S, 21.4%).

On reduction with hydrogen sulphide in presence of aqueous or ethanolic ammonia shining yellow crystals were obtained which on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 185°. This was identified with 1-phenyldithiobiuret (From *m.étal.*, *Annalen*, 1893, 275, 34). The original product could not therefore be a benzothiazolyli derivative.

(IV). *N*-2-Benzothiazolyli cyanamide.

Dilute ethereal solutions of the appropriate 2-aminobenzothiazole and half the molecular quantity of bromocyanogen were mixed and kept for 1 to 2 hours at 40-60°. Reaction proceeded with the separation of the hydrobromide of the starting aminobenz-

thiazole. The cyanamide formed was retained in the ethereal solution and was separated from the hydrobromide by filtration, followed by evaporation of the ether. Thus was obtained a mixture of unchanged aminobenzothiazole and its cyanamide. In the case of 2-benzothiazolyl- and 2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl-cyanamides, separation of the pure cyanamide was effected by extraction with alkali in which these were soluble and could be reprecipitated by just acidification.

The 3-methyl-2-benzothiazolyl cyanamide is not very soluble in ether. It was precipitated along with the hydrobromide; so the cyanamide was separated by washing the unchanged aminobenzothiazole and its hydrobromide with cold dilute acid.

6-Methyl-2-methylaminobenzothiazole afforded a cyanamide which was dimorphous. One form is soluble in ether and the other insoluble.

Cyanamides were prepared from the following aminobenzothiazoles: (i) 2-amino-, (ii) 6-methyl-2-amino-, (iii) 3-methyl-2-imino-, (iv) 2-methylamino-, (v) 6-methyl-2-methylamino-, (vi) 2-phenylamino-. These were crystallised from absolute ethanol and chlorobenzene. The physical characteristics and results of analyses are recorded in Table I.

N-2-Benzothiazolylthiocarbamides.—The *N-2-benzothiazolyl* cyanamides, obtained above, were treated with ethanolic ammonium hydrogen sulphide solution and the mixture was boiled for about 20 to 30 minutes. The cyanamides first went into solution; on continued boiling the related thiocarbamides were precipitated. These were collected after cooling the reaction mixture and crystallised from solvents like absolute ethanol and chlorobenzene in shining crystals. All the cyanamides except 3-methyl-2-benzothiazolylcyanamide could be thiohydrolised into the related thiocarbamides. All the thiocarbamides were desulphurizable with sodium plumbite solution. *N-2-benzothiazolyl*-, and *N-2-(6-methyl)benzothiazolyl*-thiocarbamides were found soluble in cold alkali and to precipitate the corresponding cyanamides on acidification. All the thiocarbamides melted with decomposition with evolution of hydrogen sulphide. Their physical characteristics and results of analyses are summarised in Table II.

N-2-Benzothiazolyl-S-benzylisothiocarbamides.—*N-2-benzothiazolyl*thiocarbamides and benzyl chloride in equimolecular proportion were refluxed in absolute ethanol for 30 to 40 minutes. The clear solution on cooling threw out crystals of the related isothiuronium chlorides. Equivalent weights of these hydrochlorides were determined titrimetrically. Free bases were prepared and crystallised from dilute ethanol. Analyses, physical characteristics and equivalent weights are recorded in Table III.

N-2-Benzothiazolyl carbamides.—The cyanamide (1g.) and HCl (conc., 20 c.c.) were boiled under reflux for about 1 hour. The cyanamide dissolved at first forming a clear solution; on continued boiling a white fluffy precipitate was thrown out. On filtration and crystallisation from acetic acid, needle-shaped crystals were obtained. These were the related carbamides. The results of these experiments are summarised in Table IV.

In the case of 2-amino-, 2-amino-(6-methyl)-, and 3-methyl-2-iminobenzothiazoles, the corresponding carbamides were also obtained by heating these benzothiazoles with cyanamide at 130-40° for 5 to 10 minutes. These were found to melt at 300°, 408°, and

TABLE I
N-2-Benzothiazolylcyanamides.

No. Resonants,	Solvent.	Cyanamide formed. (Yield).	Colour.	Formula.	Cryst. form.	M.P.	Found.	Calc.	Remarks.
1. 2-Amino-BT† + BrCN	Ether (Sulphuric)	N-2-BT-cyanamide (30%)	White	C ₈ H ₅ N ₃ S	Absolute ethanol	181°	C: 55.15% H: 2.85 N: 23.93 S: 16.42	54.85% 2.85 24.00 18.28	Soluble in alkali & acid. Titratable against alkali. Equiv. found, 179.3. C ₈ H ₅ - N ₃ S requires equiv., 175.
2. 2-Amino- (6-methyl)- BT + BrCN	Do	N-2-(6-Methyl)-BT- cyanamide (35%)	"	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ S	"	193°	C: 56.96 H: 3.96 N: 21.89 S: 17.24	57.14 3.70 22.22 16.93	Soluble in alkali & acid. Tit- ratable against alkali. Equiv. found, 192.4; C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ S requires equiv., 189.
3. 3-Methyl-2- imino-BT + BrCN	Ether-ben- zene mixture	N-2-(3-Methyl)- BT-cyanamide (80-90%)	Greenish yellow	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ S	Benzene- ethanol mixture	175°	C: 57.00 H: 3.58 N: 21.85 S: 16.73	57.14 3.70 22.22 16.93	Insoluble in alkali and acid.
4. 2-Methyl- amino-BT + BrCN	Ether	N-2-(N-Methyl)- BT-cyanamide (80-90%)	White	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ S	Absolute ethanol	102°	C: 57.31 H: 3.78 N: 21.89 S: 16.83	57.14 3.70 22.22 16.93	Do
5. 2-Methyl- amino- (6-methyl)- BT + BrCN	Ether	N-2-(N-Methyl)- (6-methyl)- BT-cyanamide (80-85%) (ether soluble)	"	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₃ S	"	*104°	C: 59.49 H: 4.69 N: 20.36 S: 16.02	59.11 4.40 20.68 15.76	"
6. Do	"	Do (ether insoluble) (20%)	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₃ S	Chloro- benzene	*168°	N: 20.76 S: 15.91	20.68 15.76	"
7. 2-Phenyl- amino-BT + BrCN	Benzene	N-2-(N-Phenyl)- BT-cyanamide (90%)	White	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ S	Absolute ethanol	132°	C: 66.99 H: 3.64 N: 16.54 S: 12.68	66.93 3.58 16.73 12.74	"

† BT represents benzothiazole.

* Dimorphic forms of the cyanamide.

TABLE II
N-2-Benzothiazolythiocarbamides.

S. No.	Cyanamide thio- hydrolysed.	Thiocarbamide formed (yield).	Colour.	Formula.	Cryst. form.	M.P.	Found.	Calc.	Remarks.
1.	<i>N-2-BT-cyanamide</i>	<i>N-2-BT-thiocarbamide</i> (80%)	Yellow	$C_9H_7N_3S_2$	Absolute ethanol	209°	C : 46.21% H : 3.63 N : 20.08 S : 30.84	45.99% 3.39 20.09 30.62	Soluble in cold alkali; cyanamide precipitated on neutralisation.
2.	<i>N-2-(6-Methyl)-BT-cyanamide</i>	<i>N-2-(6-Methyl)-BT-thiocarbamide</i> (80%)	White	$C_9H_9N_3S_2$	Do	212°	C : 48.39 H : 4.68 N : 18.72 S : 28.69	48.43 4.03 18.83 28.69	Soluble in cold alkali; cyanamide precipitated on neutralisation.
3.	<i>N-2-(N-Methyl)-BT-cyanamide.</i>	<i>N-2-(N-Methyl)-BT-thiocarbamide</i> (80-90%)	"	$C_9H_9N_3S_2$	Chloro- benzene	159°	C : 48.49 H : 4.35 N : 18.72 S : 28.41	48.43 4.03 18.83 28.69	Insoluble in cold alkali.
4.	<i>N-2-(6-Methyl-N-methyl)-BT-cyanamide (104°)</i>	<i>N-2-(6-Methyl-N-methyl)-BT-thiocarbamide</i> (75-80%)	Faint yellow	$C_{10}H_{11}N_3S_2$	Do	*181°	C : 50.86 H : 4.79 N : 17.81 S : 27.24	50.63 4.64 17.72 27.00	Do; mixed m.p. of 181° and 199° did not show any depression.
5.	Do (188°)	Do	Deep yellow	$C_{10}H_{11}N_3S_2$	"	*109°	N : 17.70 S : 27.12	17.72 27.00	
6.	<i>N-2-(N-Phenyl)-BT-cyanamide.</i>	<i>N-2-(N-Phenyl)-BT-thiocarbamide</i>	White	$C_{14}H_{11}N_3S_2$	Ethanol	195°	N : 14.64 S : 22.59	14.74 22.45	Insoluble in cold alkali.

* The thiocarbamides are dimorphous.
 BT represents benzothiazolyl.

TABLE III
N-2-Benzothiazolyl-*S*-benzylisothiuronium chlorides.

No.	Reactants.	Isothiuronium chloride.	M.P.	Equivalent weight.		Free base m.p.	Found.	Calc.
				Found.	Calc.			
1.	<i>N</i> -2-BT-thiocarbamide + BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-BT- <i>S</i> -benzyliso-T	212°	337.6	335.5	78° (C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂)	C: 59.95% H: 4.35 N: 13.87	60.20% 4.34 14.04
		(C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)						
2.	<i>N</i> -2-(6-Methyl)-BT- thiocarbamide + BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-(6-Methyl)-BT- <i>S</i> - benzyliso-T	201°	352.2	349.5	118° (C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂)	C: 61.17 H: 4.77 N: 13.12	61.34 4.79 13.41
		(C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)						
3.	<i>N</i> -2-(<i>N</i> -Methyl)-BT- thiocarbamide + BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-(<i>N</i> -Methyl)-BT- <i>S</i> -benzyliso-T	235°	348.7	349.5	71° (C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂)	C: 61.66 H: 4.84 N: 13.48	61.34 4.79 13.41
		(C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)						
4.	<i>N</i> -2-(<i>N</i> -Methyl- 6-methyl)-BT- thiocarbamide + BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-(<i>N</i> -Methyl-6- methyl)-BT- <i>S</i> -benzyliso-T	242°	365.3	363.5	155° (C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂)	N: 13.00	12.84
		(C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)						
5.	<i>N</i> -2-(<i>N</i> -Phenyl)-BT- thiocarbamide + BzCl	<i>N</i> -2-(<i>N</i> -Phenyl)-BT- <i>S</i> -Benzyliso-T	150°	408.5	411.5	139° (C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂)	N: 11.15	11.2
		(C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)						

BzCl represents benzyl chloride.

BT represents benzothiazolyl.

T " " thiuronium chloride.

TABLE IV

N-2-Benzothiazolylicarbamides.

Cyanamide hydrolysed.	Carbamide formed.	Colour.	Cryst. from.	M.P.	Found.	Calc.
1. <i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolylicyanamide	<i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolylicarbamido. (C ₈ H ₇ ON ₃ S)	White	Gl. acetic acid.	*300°		
2. <i>N</i> -2-(6-Methyl)benzothiazolylicyanamide	<i>N</i> -2-(6-Methyl)benzothiazolylicarbamide (C ₉ H ₉ ON ₃ S)	„	Do	*308°		
3. <i>N</i> -2-(3-methyl)benzothiazolylicyanamide	<i>N</i> -2-(3-Methyl)benzothiazolylicarbamide (C ₉ H ₉ ON ₃ S)	Greenish yellow	Chlorobenzene	230°	N : 20.05 S : 15.61	20.28 15.45
4. <i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolylicyanamide	<i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolylicarbamide (C ₈ H ₇ ON ₃ S)	White	Do	187°	N : 20.12	20.28
5. <i>N</i> -2-(6-Methyl)benzothiazolylicyanamide	<i>N</i> -2-(6-Methyl)benzothiazolylicarbamide (C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ON ₃ S)	„	Gl. acetic acid	234°	N : 18.06	19.00
6. <i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolylicyanamide	<i>N</i> -2-Benzothiazolylicarbamide (C ₈ H ₇ ON ₃ S)	„	Do	156°	N : 15.56	15.61

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230° respectively. These were identical with those obtained by hydrolysis of the related cyanamides (vide Table IV).

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